

On Odoratin

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Two new syntheses of odoratin (1) are reported.

ODORATIN (5,6,7-trimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavone) was isolated from *Dipteryx odorata* Willd. (Aubl.) and synthesised by Nakano *et al.*¹. Very recently further confirmation of its structure came from the work of Bhardwaj *et al.*². Our synthetical work, essentially complete some years back, had a different albeit conventional approach: (i) the first involved a Wessely—Moser rearrangement of the known isoflavone (2b) and (ii) by the cyanohydrin approach employing the ketone (4) (*vide* Experimental). In each case, the physical constants of synthetic odoratin agreed with those of the natural product.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Nmr spectrum was recorded in CDCl₃ with TMS as an internal reference. The infrared spectrum was recorded on Perkin-Elmer 237 and 577 spectrophotometers.

2-Hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenyl-3,4-methylenedioxybenzyl ketone: Under an atmosphere of dry nitrogen 1,2,3,5-tetramethoxybenzene (2.0 g) in anhydrous ether (20 ml) was added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.5 g) in anhydrous ether (25 ml) followed by the addition of 3,4-methylenedioxyphenylacetyl chloride (2.5 g) in anhydrous ether (20 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at 0° for 3 h and then left overnight. Next day, ether was removed from the oily residue by decantation, and the oil was washed with anhydrous ether (3 × 10 ml) and then treated with 15% aqueous hydrochloric acid (40 ml) at 0°. The product was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed successively with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and extracted with 10% sodium hydroxide solution; the aqueous solution was then acidified after cooling. The solid that separated out was crystallised from ether as pale yellow needles, m.p. 117-18° (lit.¹, 103°) (Found: C, 62.35; H, 5.45. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₈O₇: C, 62.42; H, 5.61%); ν_{max} 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=O); nmr δ (90 MHz) 3.78 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.89 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.91 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.22 (2H, s, COCH₂Ph), 5.91 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.67 (3H, br, s, 2', 5', 6'-H), 6.73 (1H, s, 5-H), 13.60 (1H, s, OH); *m/z* 346 (*M*⁺, 48%).

5,7,8-Trimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavone (2a): A suspension of powdered sodium (400 mg) in dry ethyl formate (50 ml) was added under an atmosphere of dry nitrogen to a solution of the above deoxybenzoin (400 mg) in dry ethyl formate (40 ml). The mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then excess of sodium metal was decomposed by adding ethanol. Subsequently concentrated hydrochloric acid was added and the

mixture was warmed on water-bath for 15-20 min. On working up in the usual manner a solid that separated was crystallised from benzene as yellow needles, m.p. 181° (lit.¹, 181°) (Found : C, 63.72 ; H, 5.11. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{14}O_7$: C, 64.04 ; H, 4.53%) ; ν_{\max} 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=O).

5-Hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavone (2b) : 5,7,8-Trimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavone (2a) (1.0 g) was dissolved in dry acetonitrile (70 ml) and the solution refluxed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5 g) for 2 h on a water-bath. The solvent was removed and the complex was decomposed by heating with cold dilute hydrochloric acid (25 ml) for 15 min and the product filtered. It was crystallised from ethanol-ethyl acetate as yellow needles, m.p. 192-93° (m.m.p. with 5,7,8-trimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavone showed a depression, m.p. 164-65°) (Found : C, 62.97 ; H, 5.53. $C_{18}H_{14}O_7$ requires : C, 63.16 ; H, 4.12%) ; ν_{\max} 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=O) ; *m/z* 342 (M^+ , 48%), 327 (base peak), 328 (20%), 146 (10%), 181 (2%).

5-Hydroxy-6,7-dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavone (3) : The above isoflavone (2b) (0.5 g) was refluxed with absolute methanolic potash (2%, 50 ml) for 15 min, cooled, acidified, diluted and filtered. The solid thus obtained, was crystallised from ethyl acetate-benzene as colourless silky needles, m.p. 180-81° (Found : C, 63.10 ; H, 4.14. $C_{18}H_{14}O_7$ requires : C, 63.16 ; H, 4.12%).

5,6,7-Trimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavone (odoratin) (1) : 5-Hydroxy-6,7-dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavone (3) (0.5 g), dimethyl sulphate (3 ml), anhydrous potassium carbonate (5.0 g) and dry acetone (70 ml) were refluxed for 30 h. The solvent was then removed, water added and the product was extracted with chloroform. 5,6,7-Trimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavone (0.3 g) was obtained which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as colourless needles, m.p. 174-75° (lit.¹, 179°) (Found : C, 63.97 ; H, 5.24. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{16}O_7$: C, 64.04 ; H, 4.53%) ; ν_{\max} 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=O). It showed a superimposable infrared spectrum with the authentic sample supplied by Nakano *et al.*¹ (isolated from *Dipteryx odorata* Willd.).

ω -Chloromethylenedioxyacetophenone : A mixture of piperonylic acid (3.3 g), thionyl chloride (5 ml) and dry benzene (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. Excess of thionyl chloride was then removed. A liquid residue was obtained which distilled at 155°/25 mm and on cooling afforded a solid, m.p. 80°.

Piperonyl chloride (3.1 g) in dry ether was added slowly to a cooled ethereal solution of diazomethane (dry, prepared from 14.0 g nitrosomethyl-urea) with stirring and the mixture left overnight. On the following day the solvent was removed under reduced pressure at room temperature. A solid diazoketone was obtained, m.p. 110-12°. It was then treated with hydrochloric acid at 0°.

ω -Chloromethylenedioxyacetophenone was obtained as a solid compound, m.p. 94-95° (Found : C, 54.02 ; H, 3.72. $C_9H_7O_2Cl$ requires : C, 54.40 ; H, 3.52%).

ω -3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyacetophenone (4) : A mixture of 3,4,5-trimethoxyphenol (2.0 g), ω -chloromethylenedioxyacetophenone (1.9 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5.0 g) in dry acetone (30 ml) was refluxed on water-bath for 20 h under anhydrous condition. The acetone solution was then filtered and the solvent removed under vacuum. The residual oil was taken in ether, washed with 10% sodium hydroxide solution followed by water and dried ($MgSO_4$). On removal of the solvent ω -3,4,5-trimethoxyphenoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyacetophenone separated as solid compound which was crystallised from benzene as white plates, m.p. 154-55° (Found : C, 62.40 ; H, 5.66. $C_{18}H_{14}O_7$ requires : C, 62.42 ; H, 5.20%) ; ν_{\max} 1 690 cm^{-1} (C=O).

3-Hydroxy-5,6,7-trimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavanone (6) : A solution of ω -3,4,5-trimethoxyphenoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyacetophenone (4) (1.0 g) in ether (25 ml) was stirred with a solution of potassium cyanide (4.0 g in 20 ml water). During 48 h, a 30% H_2SO_4 (15 ml) was added and stirring continued for a further 24 h. The ethereal solution was separated, washed several times with water and dried ($MgSO_4$). On removal of the solvent the cyanohydrin (5) was obtained as a liquid which was used without purification.

Powdered anhydrous zinc chloride (2.0 g) was added to a solution of the above cyanohydrin (1.5 g) in dry ether (30 ml) and the whole mixture saturated with dry hydrogen chloride for several hours and kept in a refrigerator for 5 days. Ether was then decanted and the residue washed with dry ether (3×10 ml). Water was added and the mixture refluxed for 30 min. It was then cooled when solid crystals separated which was crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 138-39° (Found : C, 60.58 ; H, 5.24. $C_{19}H_{16}O_8$ requires : C, 60.90 ; H, 4.85%) ; ν_{\max} 3 450 (OH) and 1 652 cm^{-1} (C=O).

5,6,7-Trimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavanone (odoratin) (1) : 3-Hydroxy-5,6,7-trimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyisoflavanone (0.8 g) was dissolved in cold concentrated sulphuric acid (2 ml) and water added to the fluorescent solution after 30 min. A crystalline mass separated which was filtered, washed and crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as pale yellow needles, m.p. 178-79° (lit.¹, 179°) (Found : C, 63.87 ; H, 5.13. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{16}O_7$: C, 64.04 ; H, 4.53%) ; ν_{\max} 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=O). There was no depression in m. m.p. on admixture with an authentic sample of odoratin prepared earlier.

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